

SERVICES OF MILITARY SERVICE, PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITY AND SOCIAL ADAPTATION OF FAMILY MEMBERS

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Abstract. This article describes the identity of a military serviceman, his competence, the nature of the military serviceman's adaptation to military service, the socialization process of adaptation, and the factors of social adaptation of family members.

Key words: competence of military personnel, adaptation to professional activity, socialization process, loyalty to duty, effective adaptation, professional consciousness.

Adaptation of military personnel to professional activity is a component of their competence. Competence serves to form a perfect person. The competence of military personnel is directly related to legal, psychological, pedagogical, and cybernetic knowledge. The word competence has many definitions in pedagogy and psychology, but competence is not considered the subject of the object we are studying. The competence of each military serviceman is directly related to the process of adaptation, i.e. adaptation to professional activity. "Process" means the period of education and formation of a military serviceman, which includes a certain period of time.

The word "Process" is derived from the Arabic language and means to flow, to happen, to act, to progress one after the other, and to develop. The professional activity of military personnel consists of several processes, and these processes guide military personnel to professional activity and serve to adapt them

to the service.

In our view, military servicemen's adaptation to professional activity begins from the day they put on military uniform. Because, first of all, they adapt to the military uniform, then to the environment and activities. These three factors serve to form the professional consciousness of military personnel.

First of all, professional adjustment is manifested in the attitude of each military serviceman to his duties and tasks.

Secondly, in the course of the professional activity of military personnel, it is manifested in their relationship to the requirements of the General Military Regulation.

Military personnel cannot quickly adapt to professional activities. Time is needed for this, and time should serve to acquire professional knowledge, skills and activities.

For example, we can see from practice that military servicemen undergo a training camp to adapt to professional activities, and this training camp also directly helps to determine whether military servicemen can adapt to the activity or not.

Adaptation to professional activity is a broad concept, and adaptation of servicemen to activity directly and indirectly depends on each serviceman, first of all, on himself, and then on the entities that educate them. The professional, legal, and psychological outlook of each military serviceman is also important in professional adjustment. While studying the theoretical aspects of adaptation to professional activity, we should know well that this process serves to form a perfect person.

Adaptation of military personnel to professional activity helps to realize that they are devoting themselves to free, free, state and public service. Secondly, it encourages military personnel to protect the Motherland, the President and specific national human values. Adaptation of military personnel to professional

activity is directly related to the term "socialization". "Socialization" does not have a single meaning, this term is studied in some cases as a synonym of the concept of "personal development", and in other cases it is interpreted as a term of "education". In addition, socialization is also defined in sociology. It is said that "in the process of socialization, each serviceman gains self-awareness, the ability to think and act independently." The word socialization is directly related to adaptation. Who will adapt? First of all, a well-educated military serviceman can adapt to the environment and situation. Regardless of the meaning of the word "education", it is directly and indirectly related to the words adaptation and socialization.

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Today, military servicemen's adaptation to professional activity, like all social sciences, turns the problem of military servicemen's adaptation to professional activity into a topic of debate in the theory of pedagogy.

The term "employee" has been widely studied and researched by many of

our scientists, namely V. Alimasov, N.N. Azizkhodjayeva, O.M. Askarova, I. Ismoilov, Z. Zaripov, Kh. Mamatov, U. Tadzhikhanov and R. Makhmudov. is getting married.

While noting the importance of research in the works of the above-mentioned scientists, it should be noted that the adaptation of the military serviceman and his professional activities was not studied in depth in the scientific works of these scientists, because the object of their study was focused on a different problem and some aspects of adaptation tried to illuminate in their scientific works. At the same time, adaptation to professional activity was not analyzed as a research topic.

Since history consists of the actions of individuals, social sciences, including the theory of pedagogy, are concerned with explaining these actions. Every military serviceman engaged in professional activity must know his rights, duties and responsibilities as a criterion of compliance with the laws of this country, as well as the fact that he has developed professional consciousness, culture, and education.

A military serviceman educates his behavior and professional legal consciousness while adapting to professional activity.

Today, solving the social problems of every serviceman and protecting their interests is one of the problems that must be solved at the state level. In particular, the housing problem is being solved at the state level. Yesterday, a seminar training was held in the Center of Spirituality and Enlightenment of the Central Military District for the purpose of social protection and support of the family members of military personnel in the Samarkand garrison.

First, lectures were given by representatives of the religious office in order to increase the spiritual and educational knowledge of the participants, to strengthen the ideological immunity of military personnel and their family members against foreign ideas. Concepts were given on topics such as "A woman's role in the

family", "A strong family is the foundation of society".

In order to ensure the employment of family members of military servicemen, detailed information was given about training courses and vacancies in service and service specialties at the monocenter.

Today, the highest goal of any organization is to serve the people and please the representatives of the population. Improving the standard of living of the population and reducing the problems they face in their lives is becoming the main principle of the fair policy conducted in our country. Organized as a consistent continuation of the ongoing reforms, the mobile reception is also aimed at listening to appeals and solving problems positively.

In order to study and positively solve the social problems of military personnel and their family members, a mobile reception was organized in the military unit of the Bostonliq district of the Tashkent region under the Ministry of Defense. It includes the commander of the troops for the protection of classified objects, the deputy military prosecutor of the Republic, the employees of the public education, preschool education departments, the employment assistance department and the housing use department, and other state organizations participated.

At the event, the problems of military servicemen and their family members were studied, and it was determined that relevant organizations would conduct studies on them.

At the same time, officials gave full answers to the questions of military servicemen and their family members at the event. Problematic issues related to housing and pre-school education were considered in this place, some appeals were controlled, and instructions were given to those in charge to ensure their implementation in a short period of time.

During the mobile reception, the Employment Assistance Center for providing employment to the family members of military personnel organized a

job fair in state organizations and associations. he was provided with a certain job.

A military serviceman who is a part of a person is the object and subject of history. According to Professor U. Tadjikhanov, "The individual is the main object of the educational process." Therefore, the study of a military serviceman is also an object of the educational process.

In conclusion, it should be said that the adaptation of military personnel to professional activity indicates that they have a high culture and we think that it is one of the criteria that shows the degree to which every military personnel is ready to defend the Motherland in front of the Motherland, the people, and the President.

Studying the theoretical and historical aspects of each problem directly helps to choose and study the methodology of this problem. Adaptation of military personnel to professional activities and social adaptation of family members depends on factors that serve to enrich the content of their formation, such factors include:

1. Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
2. Speeches of the President in his works;
3. General Military Regulations of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
4. Orders and instructions;
5. The participation of every military serviceman in the maintenance of public order;
6. Participation in enlightenment classes;
7. Participation in moral courts;
8. By conducting individual interviews;
9. Through socio-political studies;
10. Through physical and combat training;
11. Participating in social and political events held in the places of service.

Adaptation of military personnel to professional activity does not mean that they will fully comply with the Military Regulations, for this, it is necessary to develop professional skills, professional consciousness, and a sense of patriotism in every military personnel. Professional skill, professional experience is a direct product of professional adaptation.

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